

Location

Finland (Southern Finland – Pusula, Joutseno, Laitila)

Key Issues

- » Frequent use of **deep inversion ploughing** in organic cereal farming → negatively affects soil organisms, especially earthworms.
- » **Conventional early potato farming** with very short cultivation periods (1–1.5 months).
- » **Prolonged bare soil exposure** → erosion, nutrient leaching, and carbon emissions.
- » **Soil chemistry imbalances** and deterioration of physical structure.
- » **Long-term profitability may be compromised.**

SoildiverAgro Approach

Case studies focused on early potatoes and cereals, testing:

- » **Deep moldboard ploughing vs. long-term minimum tillage.**
- » Use of **catch crops** (*Phacelia* or rye + Westerwolds ryegrass) in early potato fields.
- » Use of **forest industry side-stream amendments** (from pulp mills) as soil inputs.
- » Main objective: Reduce the negative effects of bare soil and deep tillage, while **enhancing soil biodiversity** and maintaining or improving crop yields.

Benefits

- » **Spring ploughing protects soil life.**
- » **Catch crops offer pest control potential.**
- » **Forest amendments support circular economy.**
- » **Minimum tillage improves biodiversity.**
- » **Long-term research enables adaptive farming.**

Deep inversion ploughing is still often applied in organic cereal farming in the Boreal region to control perennial weeds. However, **deep ploughing as a tillage method is reported to negatively affect many soil organisms**, particularly larger soil animals such as earthworms. Conventional early potato farming is facing agricultural challenges due to its short cultivation period (1–1.5 months) and the prolonged exposure of bare soil, which is prone to **erosion, nutrient leaching and carbon emission from the soil**, resulting in environmental pressures, imbalances in soil chemistry and deterioration of physical structure. This can lead to decreased profitability in the longer term.

Given these challenges, specific sustainable agricultural strategies have been tested in Southern Finland in the case studies conducted as part of the **SoildiverAgro Project**. Case studies carried out in Pusula, Joutseno, and Laitila focused on early potatoes or cereals as the primary crops, including a) **sudden deep moldboard ploughing versus long-term minimum tillage**; b) **use of catch crops (*Phacelia* or a mix of rye and Westerwolds ryegrass) in early potato fields**; c) **use of soil amendments processed from side-streams of forest industry (pulp mills) in early potato fields.**

The main objectives of these practices were to reduce problems arising from the prolonged exposure of bare soil in early potato fields and sudden deep ploughing in long-term organic cereal fields with minimum tillage, while increasing soil biodiversity and maintaining—or even improving—agricultural yields. Improved soil biodiversity is expected to enhance overall soil health and fertility in the medium to long term, contributing to the resilience and sustainability of agricultural systems.

Results

Based on the results obtained in this project, the following policy recommendations are proposed:

1. **Deep inversion tillage with moldboard ploughing in organic wheat farming should not be promoted without well-judged reason** (e.g. persistent weed problems or phosphorus runoff), as it is not a cost-effective tillage method for farmers.
2. The impacts of occasional ploughing on soil organisms are not detrimental, however **springtime ploughing in Boreal cereal field should be promoted instead of autumn ploughing if possible.**
3. The sowing of catch crop species in Boreal early potato fields does not appear to be profitable for farmers in the short term. However, **farmers have an opportunity to utilise the current environmental compensation system by growing *Phacelia* as a catch crop after harvesting early potatoes.**
4. **Since potential beneficial effects of catch crops on pest and disease control in early potato fields were observed, long-term investigations are needed to confirm these benefits.** Research should focus on the species and varieties of catch crops (e.g. *Phacelia*), both grown individually and in mixtures, as well as on the methods for pest and disease control.
5. **It is recommended to explore the benefits of catching crops in other systems than monocultures, i.e., more diverse crop rotations in Boreal early potato farming.**
6. **The short-term use of forest-derived recycled organic soil amendments based on side-streams in Boreal early potato fields cannot be recommended without reservation,** as they incurred extra costs for farmers due to decreased gross margins.
7. **Long-term investigations are needed to verify the benefits of organic soil amendments derived from the forest industry,** especially since no harmful effects on soil biology were detected during the project period.
8. **The potential of organic side-streams as soil amendments to complement fertilisers and support the circular economy should be further investigated at both EU and national levels.** This is also linked to the broader issue of national supply security.

From the **SoildiverAgro** Project's perspective, the implementation of these policy recommendations would assist in choosing management tools that are profitable while also enhancing the long-term resilience and sustainability of agricultural systems—primarily through improved biodiversity and enhanced soil ecosystem services.

